

PROSPECTS FOR BOOSTING ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITIES IN NIGERIA'S TOURISM INDUSTRY

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Abstract: The future of Nigeria's economic resurgence lies in its ability to increase global relevance. One of the major ways of doing so is through the strategic use of available resources to produce world-class goods and services in the tourism sector. Unfortunately, Nigeria's tourism sector remains underexplored and often mismanaged. Entrepreneurial activities are relatively low. Therefore, this study combs the existing literature to examine the various types of tourism, highlight the immense benefits inherent in tourism, and examine entrepreneurial activities in tourism. Secondary data were obtained from published academic materials, such as conference presentations, theses, referred journal articles, and other relevant documents. Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses were used to achieve the set objectives. The study also highlighted numerous factors hindering tourism and a framework to boost entrepreneurial activities in Nigeria's tourism sector. This study contributes to the existing literature by presenting broader viewpoints and discussions about tourism and entrepreneurial activities in terms of the volume of studies, journal outlets, research methods, themes, index, and countries where numerous studies were conducted. Furthermore, the study is a clarion call toward promoting tourism and, by extension, entrepreneurial activities in Nigeria.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurial Activities, Tourism, Tourism Sector, Nigeria

Introduction

The current trend of the world becoming a global village comes with massive benefits, one of which is the ability to network, the ease of mobility, and the ability to have a clearer view of different parts of the globe. This trend was stimulated by research and the quest for knowledge. The constant insatiable quest for knowledge is one of man's innate nature, which oftentimes requires movement from one part of the globe to another. Man also seeks to achieve balance and renewed vigor from time to time via relaxation, especially after long periods of work and busy schedules. This constant quest for relaxation and advancement of knowledge often stimulates tourism and justifies the need to promote tourist activities across the globe. Moreover, the reported tremendous benefits inherent in tourism catalyze nations to be intentional about actively promoting and participating in it.

Apart from its economic, psychological and sociological benefits, tourism also increases a country's relevance among nations and helps in the preservation of its endowments for posterity (Amiti & Ibraimi, 2023; Odhiambo, 2021; Prakash, Kumar & Gautam, 2020; Mahajan, 2017). It is one of the most lucrative industries with a global

impact, promoting gastronomy, human heritage and identity to mention but a few (Amiti & Ibraimi, 2023; Prakash, Kumar & Gautam, 2020). In 2022, cities like New York, Paris, Amsterdam, Dubai, Rome, London, and Madrid will welcome large numbers of international tourists annually. Furthermore, in Euromonitor International's compilation of the top 100 most visited cities, Europe had the highest representation with 40 cities (TravelPerk, 2023).

In recognition of its importance, 27th September of every year has been devoted to fostering conscientious and sustainable tourism, growing the diverse indigenous cultural heritages and diversities that tourism fetches, and promoting global understanding (UNWTO, 2015). Countries that are apt to recognize this and act in compliance use this avenue to increase and retain their relevance (Alisa & Ridho, 2020; Vanegas, 2014). Some African countries, such as Rwanda, Kenya, Gambia, and Tanzania, boast of a large annual influx of tourists and seek to generate as much income from tourism (Odhiambo, 2021; Asongu, & Odhiambo, 2019; Vanegas, 2014; Christie *et al.*, 2013), whereas many tourist centers in Nigeria suffer from neglect and mismanagement (Osinubi *et al.*, 2022; Adejumo & Amusa, 2014).

Nigeria's overdependence on crude oil proceeds and abandonment of other economically viable sectors has taken a toll on the nation's revenue, overall growth, and development (Amodu, 2018; Emediegwu & Okeke, 2017). The future of Nigeria's economic resurgence lies in its ability to increase global relevance by producing world-class goods and services in tourism and other sectors. Diverse studies and anecdotal sources, however, have shown that wealth generation and economic power are not strictly limited to the production of tangible goods but also to other factors, such as generational trends and strategic use of available limited resources to mention but a few (Gale, Gelfond, Fichtner & Harris, 2020; Sirmon & Hitt, 2003). Little wonder, some seemingly less-endowed countries boost their economies via tourism and other lucrative avenues, while a vast population of some highly endowed countries live below poverty level, Nigeria inclusive.

Therefore, this study combs the existing literature to examine the various types of tourism, highlights the numerous benefits inherent in tourism, factors hindering tourism, and possible ways to boost tourism in Nigeria.

2. Review of Existing Literature

2.1 Concept and Definitions of Tourism

The terms *travel and tourism* are occasionally used interchangeably. In this milieu, travel shares a similar definition with tourism but denotes a more resolute journey. The terms *tourism* and *tourist* are sometimes used pejoratively to imply a shallow interest in the cultures or locations visited. In contrast, *the term "traveler" is often used as a sign of distinction. The sociology of tourism has studied the cultural values underpinning these distinctions and their implications for class relations.*

Tourism is a social, cultural, and economic occurrence which involves the movement of people to countries or places outside their normal surroundings for personal, business, or professional reasons. Such people are called visitors (which may be either tourists or excursionists; residents or non-residents), and tourism is associated with their activities, some of which imply tourism expenditure. Therefore, whenever people need to travel, either to explore or discover new lands or for personal enjoyment, tourism comes to mind and has stimulated diverse studies and discussions. Tourism is now basically described as a cultural, economic, and social phenomenon that entails the migration of people to cities, places, or countries outside their usual milieu for personal, career, or business purposes.

Numerous definitions have emerged in the discourse and studies of the concept tourism. In 1941, Hunziker and Kraft defined tourism as the totality of phenomena and relationships emanating from the travels and stay of non-

residents, in so far as they do not become permanent residents and are not connected with any income-earning activity. In 1976, the Tourism Society of England defined tourism as the momentary, brief movement of people, for all purposes, to destinations outside their usual places of abode and jobs as well as their activities while staying at each destination. In 1981, the International Association of Scientific Experts in Tourism also defined tourism with respect to specific activities undertaken outside their homes. (Amiti & Ibraimi, 2023; Kumar & Rai, 2017). Tourism has both conceptual and technical definitions. The conceptual definition focuses on the core meaning of tourism, while the technical definition evaluates and measures the value of tourism, which varies from one country to another. The conceptual definition describes tourism as a temporary short-term movement of persons to destinations separate from their places of abode and occupation and activities while staying at these places; including movements for all purposes, excursions, and day visits. The technical definition portrays tourism as people's activities during their travel and stay in places separate from their usual places of abode, for a continuous period of less than a year, for business, leisure, or other reasons (Gabdrakhmanov et al., 2016; WTO, 1993).

2.2 Forms and Types of tourism

As discussions on tourism continue to increase across the globe, attempts have been made to identify, stratify, and classify tourist activities. Cohen (1972) developed a fourfold tourist typology based on the degree of familiarity and novelty in travel. He categorized tourists as individual mass, organized mass, drifters, and explorers (Stainton, 2023; Stergiou & Airey, 2018). In 1994, the United Nations identified three forms of tourism based on the country of departure and destination: domestic, inbound, and outbound. They also presented three additional forms of tourism as derivatives of the three initial forms of tourism. Domestic tourism comprises persons traveling within their home countries. Inbound tourism refers to non-residents traveling within a given country, whereas outbound tourism involves residents traveling in another country. The derivatives of these three initial forms of tourism include national, regional, and international tourism. National tourism is a combination of outbound and domestic tourism, regional tourism is a combination of inbound and domestic tourism, and international tourism combines outbound and inbound tourism (TravelPerk, 2023; Camilleri & Camilleri, 2018). On types of tourism, discussions from anecdotal sources and authors' submissions are based on diverse nomenclature. TravelPerk (2023) described eight major types based on travelers' needs, motivations, and goals. Arunmozhi & Panneerselvam (2013) and Mahajan (2017) described five major types of tourism in India, including pilgrimage, heritage, Ecotourism, Wildlife and Adventure tourisms while the other types, including nature, cultural, educational, wellness, leisure, sports, and cruise tourism. Figure 1 shows trends and advancement from typology to forms and then increase in the number of main types of tourism identified by authors as an increasing number of studies are being conducted.

Figure 1: Tourism typology, forms, and types

2.3 Components and Importance of Tourism

Apart from being one of the fastest growing industries, tourism is also a prime job provider since globalization took a different turn (Reali, 2023; Folarin & Adeniyi, 2020). The sector has moved from regular air travel and field trips to the entire experiences connected with tourists’ ambitions and terminuses. This new trend is not only induced by tourists’ growing income levels but also by their new ways of life and an increasing population of new breed of tourists. Progressively, people are traveling globally in order to have new life-enriching experiences of others cultures, alfresco, and education. This, in turn, provides new prospects for the tourism industry with the increasing number of local and global tourists.

In order to have a complete and well-fulfilling tourism experience, five basic components, also known as the five ‘A’s of the tourism industry, must exist (Poudel, 2025; Lin *et al.*, 2020). They are accessibility, accommodation, attraction, amenities, and activities. Accessibility refers to tourists’ capability to reach their desired destinations. It covers the various modes of transportation that must be well scheduled, comfortable, safe, and economical. Accommodation comprises the primary and secondary locations where tourists would stay and have food on arrival. The primary accommodations include resorts and hotels, etc. while the secondary accommodations include vacation centers, youth hostels, and motels.

The third component, Attraction, which could be either natural or man-made, means that the places visited must be appealing and make tourists want to return. Natural attractions such as mountains, beaches and climates, etc. and man – made attractions such as museums, historical monuments, and theme parks, etc. leave lasting impressions on people and make them want to revisit such places and inform others about them. The fourth, amenities, are basic facilities such as roads, drinking water, public toilets, and telecommunications, which some tourists may take for granted but must be provided. The fifth activity is the artificial and natural entertainment provided for tourists in each location. Combined with natural activities such as fishing and sea bathing, artificial activities such as water parks and entertainment parks help tourists build fond memories of the visited locations.

Globally, many third world nations are giving due recognition to the tourism industry and declaring specialized tourism policies to further enhance tourism in their nations for two major reasons. First, tourism requires smaller capital investments and does not often require any business gestation period. Second, it provides employment to large populations ranging from unskilled to skilled workers. Moreover, tourism offers numerous benefits such as developing lives with rich experiences, encouraging economic development, gaining respect from other external cultures, and promoting transnational cooperation and global peace (Reali, 2023; Odhiambo, 2012; Folarin & Adeniyi, 2020).

Prominent Factors affecting Tourism Across the globe

Before dovetailing into the factors crippling the Nigerian tourism industry, it is essential to examine the challenges on a global scale. Globally, all countries are not on the same pedestal; hence, they are often classified using various nomenclatures. Some countries are classified as highly industrialized or advanced, while others are called emerging or developing economies. The third category is underdeveloped or third world countries (Basel, Gopakumar & Rao, 2021; Sarda, Karmarkar & Lakhotia, 2019). In another clime, these countries are sometimes stratified based on their income levels and are referred to as low, upper-middle, lower-middle, and high-income countries. The World Bank sometimes classifies countries by regions, resource allocation, income levels, and lending powers. By extension, this implies that the volume of activities and revenue in each country’s tourism industry will not be the same. However, as shown in Table 1, some common factors are known to affect many countries’ tourism industry (Amanawa, 2022; Prakash, Kumar & Gautam, 2020; Lock 2020; Mahajan, 2017) as shown in Table1.

Table 1. Factors Affecting Global Tourism

No.	Factors	Explanations
1	Pandemic	Tourist activities are often at their lowest and badly hit whenever a disease outbreak occurs. For instance, tourist travel, activities, and revenues dropped massively in all nations of the world during the Covid 19 outbreak in 2019. Business activities within the tourism industry, such as hotels, airlines and restaurants were badly hit. Some businesses had to downsize and restructure their payment packages, while others went bankrupt.
2	Infrastructure	Many tourist destinations have outdated and poor infrastructure, which discourages tourist activities. Government agencies, tourist organizations, and destination marketing groups must collaborate to improve the existing infrastructure to boost the tourism industry. For instance, good road networks, speedier airport entry, better public transit, faster check-out procedures in hotels, and interpreting gadgets and services at airports, stations, and sea ports will enhance tourist activities.
3	Political Stability	A country’s governance structure often impacts tourism regulations, such as travel visas, border entry regulations, and the right to paid holidays. In addition, instability or political insurgence often hinders tourist activities. One of the side effects of political instability on tourism is the increasing influence of government travel advisories on travelers’ destination choices. For instance, in war-torn areas and politically unstable regions, travel advisories are often issued or bans imposed to debar tourists from traveling.

4	Security	The assurance of the safety of lives and properties is one of the stimulating factors for tourists and travelers. The efficiency of local and state police departments, city councils, and local governments can help achieve this goal. Increasing tourists' security and alertness without suffocating their experiences within each country is a plus, whereas the opposite will scare tourists away.
5	Marketing Strategies	When perceived as insufficient, false, or overstated, travel marketing can discourage tourists. Advertising agents and organizations must establish unique marketing strategies to attract the new generation of informed and discerning tourists. Likewise, technological variations and social media impact indicate that this is an era of opportunity and risks. Hence, travel marketers must adopt relevant machinery and ingenuity to attract more tourists.
6	Globalization	Uniform benchmarks and customs are often developed due to globalization. Tourism businesses must strive to provide items that enable tourists to have fun memories and do exciting things that they have never done before. In contemporary tourism ambitions, novelty is a crucial component. As a result of globalization, for instance, tourism establishments and travel businesses must fathom how to and be able to communicate with global visitors, provide necessary travel information and signage, and ensure that tourists enjoy the "home away from home" treatment.
7	Taxation	Tourism is often featured as one of the most heavily levied industries. An ingenious examination of the taxes paid for hotel reservations and plane tickets reveals that taxation has a significant impact on tourism. People travel more when the rates are low. So, in order to balance the equation, the travel organization and tourism businesses must provide competitively priced products and services. Governments must also recognize that travel shopping, tourists' purchases, and other tourism expenses already contribute to their local economies.

Source: Compiled by the author

Entrepreneurial Tourism Activities

Moyle, Moyle, and Burgers (2020) examined entrepreneurship strategies and tourism growth. They analyzed entrepreneurial strategies in 481 tourism policy and planning documents and found that regions with dedicated strategies for entrepreneurship forecast tourism growth plus the fact that the most effective strategies are those targeted toward human capital advancement and tourism incubation programs. They concluded that applying the right entrepreneurial strategies can be a powerful vehicle for regional growth.

For countries solely dependent on tourism for survival, tourist activities must be deliberately promoted to harness in inherent tourism potentials for economic development of such countries. Therefore, entrepreneurs and relevant stakeholders must be able to project and harness the intangible and tangible tourism resources in each economy (Richards, 2009 & 2007). These intangible and tangible tourism resources (Figure 2) hold unending streams of benefits if well explored.

Figure 2: Tourism Resources

2.3 Tourism in Nigeria

Nigeria recorded its foremost and major international tourist visit in 1472 when Portuguese merchants visited Lagos for trading opportunities. The federal government created Nigerian Tourist Association (NTA) in 1962 with the directive to encourage domestic and worldwide tourism in the country. The association flourished so well within two years of operation that it became a member of the International Union of Official Travel Organization (IUOTO) in 1964, which later metamorphosed into the World Tourism Organization (WTO).

The NTA was eventually dissolved in 1976, and the Nigerian Tourism Board (NTB) was inaugurated to take its place. When the Ministry of Trade and Industry (MTI) was established in 1990, and the NTB became a business corporation, the sector's growth accelerated (Amanawa, 2022).

Another group of scholars associated Nigeria's tourism progress with the adoption of Decree No.54 In 1976. This Decree became effective in 1978 and empowered the Nigerian Tourism Board (NTB) to

1. Provide tourism information advisory services;
2. Classify and rate hotels in a prescribed manner.
3. Undertake and promote tourism-related research activities;
4. Encourage indigens to have their holidays within Nigeria and encourage people in the diaspora to visit Nigeria;

2. Support the provision and upgrading of tourist amenities and major and ancillary facilities in Nigeria.

In 1992, NTA became the Nigerian Tourism Development Corporation (NTDC), a parastatal of the Federal Ministry of Culture, Tourism, and National Orientation. The Nigerian Tourism Development Corporation (NTDC) is in charge of tourism scheduling, promotion, and development. NTDC's obligations include motivating Nigerian citizens to organize their vacations within the nation and encouraging other nationals to visit Nigeria. NTDC's obligations also include boosting the establishment, implementation, and maintenance of tourism infrastructure, services, and products in Nigeria.

Tourism is reportedly one of the world's rapidly enlarging industries, and although Nigeria is only enjoying a handful of the benefits, it still features as a diffident participant in the country's economy. For instance, Amanawa (2022) and Mulkat and Mukail (2015) reported that international tourists' arrivals improved marginally from 850,000 in 2001 to 1,550,000 in 2010, before declining to 486,000 in 2012. Boko Haram's insurgency in northern Nigeria was instrumental to this shrinkage. However, tourism upsurged in 2013 by recording a 23% increase over the previous year's arrivals.

Nigeria boasts of both natural and man-made tourist centers, with all its vast and numerous resources. Practically every state has prospective and lucrative tourist sites ranging from its tropical forests, plateaus, rivers, savannahs, hills and mountains, and other attractive locations in Lagos, Ibadan, Akwa Ibom and Kaduna to mention but a few. The Kianji Dam, Obudu Ranch, historical sites like the Slave Boats and first storey building in Nigeria, and captivating beaches in Lagos, Ibeno in Akwa Ibom, Araromi in Ibadan, and Port Harcourt Tourist Beach in Rivers State.

Nigeria's dismal tourism state is evidently not the absence of tourism sites or fascinating cultures, but rather a case of poor orientation, negligence, inadequate infrastructure, corruption, inadequate funding, insecurity, and poor implementation policies among other vices. Another frustrating factor is that Nigeria is completely dependent on crude oil revenues. Hence, this article explores the need, benefits, and opportunities that tourism offers, as well as viable recommendations on how to boost tourism and attain increasingly sustainable tourism revenue streams.

2.4 Theoretical Review

A cursory glance at some germane theoretical opinions backing the tourism-economic development nexus brings to the fore some sets of theories deeply rooted in economic philosophies that have emerged from one perspective to the other. These sets of theories reflect the tenets from which the tourism concept emerged and grew to become a global and contemporary issue. They are the theories of absolute and comparative advantage, demand and supply theory, and environmental sustainability theory.

First, Adam Smith, popularly known as the Father of Capitalism, proposed the Theory of Absolute Advantage in 1776. He promulgated absolute advantage as an entity-be it individual, organization, region- or country's ability to produce more goods and services per unit of time with fewer resources or the ability to produce the same quantity with fewer resources than another individual, organization, or nation producing the same products and services. In other words, an entity with an absolute advantage can produce goods and services at the lowest total cost per unit by adopting more effective methods or fewer resources than its competitor. Thus, countries with absolute advantage should concentrate on those products and services, then use the proceeds from such products or services to import other goods and services from other nations.

According to Smith's reasoning, global advantages will abound if all nations specialize in economic activities where each has an absolute advantage and trade the products or services, so long as each nation has at least a product or service in which it has an absolute advantage over other nations (Amanawa, 2022; Potters, 2021). This theory stirred up some debates on international trade about global standards, universal product quality, and contentions that arise when a nation has no well-developed product or service to present among nations until David Ricardo, a renowned classical economist, enhanced Smith's notion of absolute advantage by suggesting the second theory known as Theory of Comparative Advantage.

Ricardo argued that international trade is more likely to grow and survive on the principle of comparative rather than absolute advantage. He posited that comparative cost variances best determine trade links between countries. That is, a country's ability to produce specific goods or services at the lowest possible cost than its other trading counterparts is referred to as comparative advantage. The comparative advantage also allows firms to sell their goods and services at cheaper rates than their competitors, resulting in higher profit borders (Amanawa, 2022; Hayes, 2020). In essence, this theory indicates that many countries' economic welfare will improve if they specialize in services and products with the lowest opportunity costs, which will invariably impact their import quotas and demand for quality global goods and services such as tourism.

Methodology

Secondary data were obtained from published academic materials, such as conference presentations, theses, referred journal articles, and other relevant documents. Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses were used to achieve the set objectives. Data were sourced from reliable online databases, such as Google Scholar, Scopus, ScienceDirect, EBSCO, and JSTOR. The obtained data were then analyzed using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA).

The documents were identified through a combination of searches using keywords and constructs that are closely associated with tourism, tourism entrepreneurship, economic growth and development. They include: tourism concepts, history and definitions across the globe, tourism in Nigeria, factors affecting tourism in Nigeria, economic growth, and environmental sustainability. There were no date restrictions on the search, but priority was solely given to the relevance of each of the materials used, with a major focus on their substantial contributions to this critical review study. Nevertheless, frantic efforts were made to capture as many recent literatures as possible, in order to reflect the aptness, germaneness, and imperativeness.

Furthermore, unrelated and irrelevant literature in the milieu of tourism, entrepreneurship, and economic development were excluded. And, in order to obviate the risk of omitting potentially relevant literature, reference lists of selected articles were appropriately scanned for materials related to the research topic under review. Thereafter, other information, such as titles and abstracts, was reviewed for articles and other publications identified in the search. Selected materials meeting pre-defined inclusion and exclusion criteria and also coherent with the research topic were included in the review. The overall inclusion criteria employed were: relevance, currency, and authority, as used by Browning and Rigolon (2019) and Wolf et al. (2014). They described relevance in relation to how the research materials had contributed to their greening discourse, currency on whether the materials were still influential regarding the debate on greening of businesses, as evidenced, for example, by citations and authority. Furthermore, currency, in terms of whether the articles had been published by reputable outlets or if the materials had been peer-reviewed or professionally edited. The initial search criteria identified 1749 materials. Then, applying the screening and eligibility processes stated above, 148 articles were identified for full-text retrieval, of which 62 met the final inclusion criteria (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Systematic Literature Review Stages

Source: Adapted from Mensah (2019) and Obisanya and Akinyemi (2024).

The full texts were read thoroughly in order to extract the relevant information. Pieces of information gathered were analyzed by combining techniques of the qualitative content analysis (Mayring 2019; Elo & Kyngäs, 2008; Hsieh & Shannon, 2005) and recursive abstraction of Polkinghorne & Arnold, (2014). Portions of information mustered through the summaries were synthesized, interwoven, and rephrased to make them more concise, condensed, coherent, and practicable, being wary not to alter the meanings when combining the themes from the data. The final output was a more succinct and polished summary of the relevant literature on the key issues of the study matter, as presented in the findings section.

Findings

1. Types of Tourism and Investment Opportunities in Nigeria

Akintunde (2025) identified nine popular types of tourism in Nigeria: educational, historical, cultural, agricultural, environmental, medical, sports, religious, and personal status enhancement tourism. Most of these types of tourism are equally prevalent in other countries, creating diverse investment opportunities for citizens. Other authors (Dinim, 2021; Alamai, Kirfi & Ladi, 2018; Ashikodi, 2010) added that timely investment in aspects such as wildlife tourism, building holiday resorts along strategic coasts, establishing hiking trails in national parks, erecting unique tourist reception hubs, spas and chalets, and erecting slave trade monuments and artifacts would further promote tourism.

2. The Holistic Benefits of Tourism

Tourism is a very important activity whose benefits transcend the immediate financial and environmental scope, especially when done entrepreneurially (Reali, 2023; Odhiamo, 2021; Moyle, Moyle & Burgers, 2020; Calmak, Lie & McCabe, 2018; Dana, Gurau & Lasch, 2014; Eruoto, 2014). Diverse literature flag the immense benefits, and some have identified some rippling effects that will impact generations to come. For instance, tourism or tourism entrepreneurship, as some may call it, has been a catalyst of some scientific discoveries, advancement of in the body of knowledge and human development, as well as regional growth and multinational trade (Moyle, Moyle & Burgers, 2020; Gabdrakhmanov *et al.*, 2016; Dana, Gurau & Lasch, 2014). Some tourists have been able to trace their genealogies and family histories, regained their cultural identities and sense of self-worth. Some couples met via tourism, and some beautiful relationships are still blossoming, thanks to tourism.

Other popular benefits highlighted in the extant literature are: improved standard of living, foreign exchange earnings; employment opportunities, utilization of local resources, infrastructural development, enhancement of cultural heritage, development of local facilities, increase in gross national product, diversification of the economy, household income generation, government revenues, global peace and cooperation, knowledge exchange, global positive image, and preservation of traditions and heritage (Reali, 2023; Odhiamo, 2021; Alisa & Ridho, 2020; Moyle, Moyle & Burgers, 2020; Calmak, Lie & McCabe, 2018; Mahajan, 2017; Yusuff & Akinde, 2015; Dana, Gurau & Lasch, 2014; Eruoto, 2014).

3. Factors hindering tourism in Nigeria

Factors hindering tourism in Nigeria could arguably be described as both systemic and attitudinal because people's actions and inaction often offshoot their people's mindset. The over-dependence on crude oil (Amodu, 2018; Emediegwu & Okeke, 2017), for instance, that led to the country being a mono-economy, is a reflection of the leaders' orientation. Oftentimes, attitudinal flaws and systemic lapses give room for unnecessary leakages and resource wastage, thereby leading to many suffering in a land filled with abundant resources (Akintunde, 2025; Amanawa, 2022). Diverse factors have been identified as hindrances to tourism, but the following are the major hitches peculiar to Nigeria (Akintunde, 2025; Osinubi *et al.*, 2022; Amanawa, 2022; Dinim, 2021; Elite, 2017): poor policy implementation, inadequate investments and funding, poor infrastructure, corruption, unsatisfactory tourism education and programs, terrorism and security challenges, insufficient tourism professionals, and health care concerns.

Finally, the absence of robust governmental policies and regulatory instruments to guide tourist activities poses a challenge to the effective implementation of tourism policies. Therefore, concerted efforts aimed at introducing useful legislation to encourage entrepreneurial activities in the tourism sector are needed.

4. Framework for Promoting Tourism in Nigeria

From the foregoing, it can be postulated that the time to promote tourism and tourism entrepreneurship in Nigeria is now. Remarkably, some efforts have been recorded in some parts of Nigeria (Akintunde, 2025; Oladele, Digun-Aweto & Merwe, 2018; Mulkat & Mukail, 2015). However, many more grounds remain to be covered, and tourist activities need to be stimulated and promoted in rural areas, towns, and cities. Hence, the necessity for a pertinent framework, well-executed projects, and effectively implemented policies and programs are necessary. Many

authors, such as Amanawa (2022) and Dinim (2021), also posited that some of the ways by which tourism can be promoted to harness its numerous benefits include the following:

1. Improved infrastructure for promoting tourist activities
2. A well-implemented tourism management board
3. Educating the public about the importance and immense benefits of tourism
4. The inclusion of ways by which tourist education and entrepreneurship as information resources at all levels of Nigeria's educational curricula.
5. Promotion and support of tourism entrepreneurs cum investment in tourist enterprises

They concluded that the promotion of tourist activities and tourism entrepreneurship can be handled at the local, state, and national levels if governments, policy makers, and all relevant stakeholders can disabuse their minds from the mono-economy syndrome and embrace the use of tourism as an economy-boosting sector.

These propositions, recommendations, and numerous other submissions can be recapitulated using a holistic framework developed for this study. The framework is based on the major stakeholders in the tourism sector, as shown in Figure 4, who can fervidly drive entrepreneurial activities in Nigeria's tourism sector. The three key players are Nigeria's policy makers and relevant stakeholders. Two: households and community leaders and three: individuals and corporate organizations interested in tourism.

Furthermore, it should be noted the effective actions of Group 1 members would simultaneously determine the type and potency of responsive actions by other key players (Groups 2 and 3) in the tourism sector. This in turn would affect collaborations and practices of tourism between Groups 2 and 3. In the same vein, the actions of Group 3 would be responses from both Groups 1 and 2. This is an all-inclusive framework toward the promotion of entrepreneurial activities in Nigeria's tourism sector, as it involves the combined efforts of every citizen in the country. The framework, if carefully adopted, would yield positive results.

Figure 4: Framework for promoting tourism in Nigeria
 Source: Author's Explanation

Conclusion

This study advances knowledge on tourism with a precise focus on the benefits and the need to promote more such enterprises in Nigeria. Entrepreneurial activities and numerous opportunities inherent in tourism were also emphasized as key and inevitable if historic and cultural heritages must be retained and economic growth must be achieved. Therefore, a framework was developed to promote infrastructure development, business activities, and technology of tourist activities using the key stakeholders' strategy. This study contributes to the existing literature by presenting broader viewpoints and discussions about tourism and entrepreneurial activities. It is a clarion call for promoting tourism and, by extension, entrepreneurial activities in Nigeria. Lastly, it will serve as a basis for future empirical investigations on the subject matter.

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